

Teaching Behavior as Moderator on the Interaction of Intercultural Sensitivity and Individual Work Performance of the Teachers

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Abstract. The current study was set to evaluate whether teaching behavior significantly moderates the relationship between intercultural sensitivity and the individual work performance of teachers. In this study, the researcher selected 188 public elementary school teachers in Calinan District, Davao City, as the respondents of the study. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and Hierarchical Regression Analysis. Descriptive analysis showed that teaching behavior and individual work performance were described as extensive, while intercultural sensitivity of teachers was rated as moderately extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between intercultural sensitivity, individual work performance, and teachers' teaching behavior in Calinan District, Davao City. Evidently, hierarchical regression analysis proved that teaching behavior significantly moderates the interaction between intercultural sensitivity and individual work performance of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City. In other words, teaching behavior was a significant moderator of teachers' intercultural sensitivity and individual work performance since it strengthened the relationship.

KEY WORDS

1. Educational management. 2. intercultural sensitivity. 3. individual work performance. 4. teaching behavior

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1. Introduction

Teachers serve as role model of behavior and positive attitudes that leads learners towards successful directions and events in their academic lives. Maintaining and demonstrating positive work values among teachers would also provide a clear image of a living example of the real essence of professionalism and integrity. The manner in which teachers deliver lessons and the way they manage classroom situations are some of the factors that may contribute to the satisfaction of students' learning and development. These are being evaluated periodically to gather data and information that will serve as the basis for continuous improvement of the university. Thus, the administration and other academe sectors may improve the teachers' work performance by motivating them to perform their duties and responsibilities.

ties effectively and efficiently. Meanwhile, the literature showed that poor work performance among teachers at all levels remains a perennial problem among administrators and policymakers worldwide (Mun et al., 2013). The report of Hales and Williamson (2010) showed that educational providers who are not enthusiastic about teaching could not create a positive influence among other teachers that would further enhance their interest in teaching jobs. Similarly, the report of Nick (2012) indicates that teachers with poor individual work performance lead to the formation of unpleasant relationships with their students and tend to experience higher levels of emotional stress and burnout and less level of well-being. Likewise, David et al. (2019) noted that the educational system in the Philippines is facing the reality of a productivity slowdown as a result of the declining work performance of employees. On the contrary, teachers with quality work performance exhibit characteristics such as engaging classroom presence, value in real-world learning, exchange of best practices, and a lifelong love of learning (Amin et al., 2013). In addition, Ida (2017) mentioned that professional knowledge, a high level of ethics, honesty, confidence, consistency, fairness, self-command, and optimism make a good teacher. More so, Esen (2011) states that teachers who have high regard for their performance in teaching jobs are more dedicated to the school organization. Likewise, Karatas and Gules (2010) expressed that teachers who find importance in individual work performance give everything for organizational goals, tend to show quality performance in teaching, take responsibility for the students, make an effort, and spend time as needed, have lower stress level but high satisfactions in teaching, and work in the organization a long time. On the one hand, Stone (2018) viewed intercultural sensitivity as the ability to discriminate and experience relevant cultural differences. Izmaylova (2017) asserted that one way to demonstrate the significance of intercultural sensitivity is to engage individuals in tasks that mirror their everyday activities and simultaneously require a certain degree of cultural awareness. Also, Kumar et al. (2018) suggested that in a culturally competent classroom environment, educators utilize the aspects of intercultural sensitivity and develop these identities by becoming more reflective, understanding, and appreciative of their own and their students' cultural identities, a more inclusive classroom culture can be acquired. Such contact can increase individuals' understanding of their cultural values, beliefs, and behaviors and could encourage them to investigate for themselves the otherness around them (Jin, 2013). On the other hand, Kangasniemi et al. (2016) defined a teacher's behavior as the set of behavioral rules that create a positive environment at work. According to Petty and Hill (2017), positive teaching behavior can lead to teachers being fairly treated, motivating them and developing a sense of loyalty towards the organization. Consequently, an individual with assertive positive behavior is an employee who has a high commitment to an organization and is subsequently more likely to make changes where such changes do not have the potential to change the fundamental values and goals of the organization and are considered beneficial for the organization, compared to individuals who are less supportive work ethic and less committed to their organization that is more likely to make changes. Several studies indicated that there exists a link between intercultural sensitivity, work performance, and teacher behavior. For instance, the study of Liu (2016) suggested that intercultural sensitivity improves individual work performance of the working individuals. Employees with high levels of intercultural sensitivity prefer to work and study in an intercultural environment and are often the catalysts in promoting team communication and improving work enthusiasm. Also, Lavicoli et al. (2018) proposed that behavior has a direct and positive

correlation with social skills, communication skills, and problem-solving skills. The more the feeling of staff with ruling ethics in the work environment, the higher the likelihood of developing employability attributes, which are essential for the future effective functioning of their organization. Most of the studies that examined the link of intercultural sensitivity to teachers' work performance were conducted in foreign settings and only examined the direct effect of intercultural sensitivity on work performance. Thus, in this context, the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Calinan District, Davao City, using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher made use of a structural equal model through hierarchical regression analysis to have a better understanding of the moderating effect of teaching behavior on the interaction of intercultural sensitivity on task performance, contextual performance, and productive work behavior of the teachers in Calinan District, Davao City which is found to be scarce.

*1.1. Review of Significant Literature—*This section discusses the variables and their indicators through various concepts and viewpoints from books, journals, and electronic sources.

*1.1.1. Intercultural Sensitivity—*Intercultural sensitivity is the ability to recognize and adapt to cultural differences (Stone, 2018). Leavitt (2010) and Spence (2016) emphasized its role in cross-cultural teaching, where mastery of cultural knowledge and skills fosters intellectual and emotional empowerment. Sandell and Tupy (2015) highlighted class discussions and interactions as pivotal for developing intercultural sensitivity. Keengwe (2010) concluded that activities such as reflective writings and experiential learning foster cultural awareness and reduce bias.

Kohli (2010) argued that cultural competence starts with self-awareness and recognizes

diverse realities. Kumar et al. (2018) stressed that inclusive classroom practices nurture understanding and appreciation of students' cultural identities. Gay (2010) and Gillespie (2019) noted that culturally sensitive teaching practices close achievement gaps and enhance teaching effectiveness. Marks (2011) and Templeton (2011) underscored the need for cultural competence training, showing its positive impact on teachers' perceptions and student outcomes.

*1.1.2. Individual Work Performance—*Koopmans et al. (2014) defined individual work performance as behaviors that align with organizational goals. Teachers' performance, driven by motivation and commitment, influences student engagement and organizational success (Klassen et al., 2012; Esen, 2011). Hakanen and Roodt (2010) highlighted the collective nature of performance, where shared positive attitudes enhance workplace dynamics. Long tenures, supported by school culture, improve engagement and outcomes (Ahuja Gupta, 2018). Similarly, Balakrishnan et al. (2013) and Imam (2014) found that non-financial drivers like recognition and teamwork foster retention.

*1.1.3. Indicators of Intercultural Sensitivity and Work Performance—*Enjoyment: Balakrishnan (2015) noted that culturally proficient individuals value diversity and engage positively across cultural environments. Confidence: Gillespie (2019) emphasized confidence in teaching diverse students as critical for cultural competence. Tolerance: Reiche (2012) and Robinson (2012) highlighted self-awareness as vital for adapting to cultural differences. Task Performance: Koopmans et al. (2014) linked task proficiency to teacher engagement, skill development, and productivity. Contextual Performance: Positive relationships with peers and stakeholders influence teachers' willingness to remain in their roles (Boyd et al., 2011; Rossi, 2018). Productive Behavior: High ethical standards and resilience enhance work engagement and organizational success (Biggs et al., 2014;

Edison et al., 2016).

1.1.4. Teaching Behavior—Teaching behavior reflects ethical and professional attitudes that create a positive work environment (Kangasniemi et al., 2016). Ethical behavior fosters loyalty and motivation among teachers (Petty Hill, 2017). Osborne and Hammoud (2017) emphasized that work ethic influences organizational commitment and the effectiveness of teaching strategies.

1.1.5. Link Between Intercultural Sensitivity and Work Performance—Liu (2016) and Yu and Chen (2010) linked intercultural sensitivity to enhanced teamwork, communication, and conflict management. Interculturally sensitive individuals show greater adaptability, confidence, and productivity, fostering positive work environments.

1.2. Synthesis—Therefore, this portion of the paper provides the researcher the result of other researches to which the present study is related or has some bearing and similarity. More so, the literature showed that intercultural sensitivity, as proposed by Balakrishnan (2015), is measured in terms of enjoyment, confidence, and tolerance, while the work performance of the teachers was contextualized by Koopmans et al. (2014) is indicated with task performance, contextual performance, and productive work behavior. Lastly, Sharma and Rai (2015) proposed that teaching behavior is the set of behavioral rules that create a positive environment at work. Hence, the above review of literature helped the researcher establish the conceptual and theoretical framework by explicitly discussing the nature of variables.

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—The study is anchored on the proposition of

The dependent variable of the study is the teachers' individual work performance or the teachers or the actions of teachers that are relevant to the organization's goals. The measures

Liu (2016) result showed that there is a significant relationship between intercultural sensitivity and work performance among working individuals. Accordingly, employees with high level of intercultural sensitivity clearly prefer to work and study in an intercultural environment. They are often the catalysts for teamwork, which are able to promote team communication and improve work enthusiasm. They can more easily become the tacit cooperation object and a close friend with other team members. In support, Iavicoli et al. (2018) proposed that behavior has a direct and positive correlation with social skills, communication skills, and problem-solving skills. The more the feeling of staff with ruling ethics in the work environment, the higher the likelihood of developing employability attributes, which are essential for the future effective functioning of their organization. This is because the dominant force of ethical behavior in organizations will reduce the negative impact of factors influencing staff attitudes and behaviors. As shown in Figure 1, the study consists of three variables. This study consists of three variables. The independent variable is the intercultural sensitivity or the ability to discriminate and experience relevant cultural differences. As proposed by Balakrishnan (2015) the measures of intercultural sensitivity are enjoyment or the ability of an individual to interact with other individuals with different culture; confidence or the perceived behavior of an individual when dealing with individuals with different cultural background; and tolerance or the ability of person to work towards understanding one's values, strengths and challenges regarding cultural difference that comes from self-realization.

of individual work performance are task performance or the proficiency with which one performs central job tasks; contextual performance or the individual behaviors that support

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

the organizational, social, and psychological environment in which the technical core must function; and productive work behavior or the behavior that does not harm the well-being of the organization. The moderating variable is the teaching behavior or the set of behavioral rules that create a positive environment at work.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The study aimed to determine the moderating effect of teaching behavior on the interaction of intercultural sensitivity on individual work performance of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City. Specifically, the study has the following objectives:

- (1) What is the extent of intercultural sensitivity of teachers in terms of:
 - (1) enjoyment;
 - (2) confidence; and
 - (3) Tolerance?
- (2) What is the extent of individual work performance of teachers in terms of:
 - (1) task performance;
 - (2) Contextual Performance and
 - (3) productive work behavior?
- (3) What is the extent of the teachers’ teaching behavior?
- (4) Is there a significant relationship between intercultural sensitivity, individual work performance, and teachers’ teaching behavior in Calinan District, Davao City?
- (5) Does teaching behavior moderate the interaction of intercultural sensitivity on the individual work performance of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City?

1.5. Hypothesis—The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance: H01: There is no significant relationship between intercultural sensitivity, individual work performance, and teachers’ teaching behavior in Calinan District, Davao City. H02:

Teaching behavior does not moderate the interaction of intercultural sensitivity on individual work performance of the teachers in Calinan District, Davao City. This study’s findings have social value because they could generate facts useful to educational institutions world-

wide to promote productive work performance among teachers. Hence, the researcher hopes that this study may benefit identified sectors of the academe, such as the Department of Education, Administrators, Teachers, Students, and Future Researchers.

1.6. Significance of the Study—Department of Education. The study's findings could provide the Department of Education with information that can be used to revise or supplement their programs to properly equip teachers with the training needed to effectively deal with stakeholders with different cultural backgrounds and improve their work performance. With intercultural sensitivity, teachers become more engaged in their work and can consider different innovative teaching methods for effective learning and internalize these. School Administrators. The study's findings may provide school administrators with a clear understanding of the underlying frameworks that support the relationship between intercultural sensitivity and the individual work performance of the teachers. Since teachers play a key role as the primary driver of learning processes and would significantly influence all aspects of the functions of the school with their behaviors, personal characteristics, and biases, teachers' perceptions regarding principal leadership styles

are critical because teachers. If we can better understand teachers' intercultural sensitivity, we may be better able to facilitate the implementation of school programs. Teachers. The findings of this study could induce self-awareness and reflection on their intercultural sensitivity and practices in view of school culture. It could initiate the teachers to assess and improve the culture at their schools and encourage them to evaluate their work performance and make an effort to match their style with the needs of their schools. Future Researchers. Other researchers would benefit from the results of this study because the findings may provide a framework and model for future research on teacher individual work performance and education management. For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were defined operationally: Intercultural Sensitivity refers to the independent variable of the study, which is described in terms of enjoyment, confidence, and tolerance. Individual Work Performance. This refers to the study's dependent variable, which is described in terms of task performance, contextual performance, and productive work behavior. Teaching Behavior. This refers to the study's moderating variable, which is expected to have a significant interaction between the independent and dependent variables.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—The study employed a non-experimental design utilizing the descriptive correlation technique of research to gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. Quantitative research deals with numbers, logic, and objective stances. It focuses on numeric and unchanging data detailed, convergent reasoning, and the generation of various ideas about a research problem

(Babbie et al., 2010). According to Myers and Well (2013), correlated design examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause-and-effect relationships between variables. It enabled the researcher to observe two variables at a point in time and helped describe the relationship of the factors of both variables. Moreover, the study also looked into the relationship among three

variables— intercultural sensitivity, individual work performance, and teaching behavior. The study investigates whether teaching behavior moderates the interaction of intercultural sensitivity on teachers' work performance in terms of task performance, contextual performance, and productive work behavior. Thus, the study only focused on the behavioral aspect—other factors that came up were not considered.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were elementary school teachers in Calinan District, Davao City. In this study, 169 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. In this study, specific inclusion criteria were implemented to determine the respondents. The primary consideration of this study is to select respondents who can provide information to achieve its purpose. Hence, only those permanent-regular elementary school teachers in Calinan District who voluntarily

The second tool is about the individual work performance of the teachers. This questionnaire was adapted from the Koopmans et al. (2014) questionnaire for individual work performance, which consists of statements divided into indicators of task performance, contextual performance, and productive work behavior. The reliability of the new scale obtained Cronbach's al-

signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions. Thus, it did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of the teachers.

2.3. Research Instrument—The study employed questionnaires adapted from different studies and was modified to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into three parts: intercultural sensitivity, teaching behavior, and individual work performance of the teachers. The scaling was done by having one-half of the value of 5 as an average cut-off point or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Before the administration of the instrument, it was subject to validation by three experts and was revised according to their expert comments. The first part of the instrument concerned intercultural sensitivity, which was adapted from the study of Balakrishnan (2015) and indicated interaction engagement/enjoyment, interaction engagement/enjoyment. The reliability of the new scale obtained Cronbach's alpha value of 0.932, which is interpreted as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. As a guide in determining the extent of intercultural sensitivity of the teachers, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

pha value of 0.946, which is interpreted as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. As a guide in determining the extent of the individual work performance of the teachers, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Intercultural sensitivity is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Intercultural sensitivity is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Intercultural sensitivity is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Intercultural sensitivity is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Intercultural sensitivity is never observed.

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Individual work performance is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Individual work performance is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Individual work performance is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Individual work performance is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Individual work performance is never manifested.

The third tool is concerned with the teaching behavior of elementary school teachers. This questionnaire was adapted from Sharma and Rai (2015). The reliability of the new scale obtained Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.938, which is interpreted as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. As a guide in determining the extent of teaching behavior, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The researcher undertook the steps in conducting the study after validating the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured permission to conduct the study and endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the principals of the selected public elementary schools in Calinan District, Davao City. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher distributed the research instrument to the respondents after the approval to conduct the study, which was conducted on April 25, 2023. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents. For the administration of the questionnaire, the study’s respondents were given enough testing time to

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teaching behavior is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teaching behavior is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teaching behavior is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teaching behavior is rarely evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teaching behavior is never evident.

finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. Then, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. *Informed Consent.* The researcher asked for the permission of respondents through written informed consent. They were properly informed about the purpose of the study, and ample explanations were given to them so that they could better understand the reason for their participation and choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that respondents' involvement in the study was voluntary. If they ever refused to participate, they were not forced to do so by the researcher. Besides, the researcher was cautious in ensuring the respondents' psychological well-being. Written permission was secured from the respondents.

The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to conduct a study on the factors that hinder/promote the teacher's behavior regarding workforce management of school heads and encouraging work environment, and may contribute to the enhancement. *Vulnerability of Research Participants.* The respondents of the study are teachers, so they are not considered vulnerable since all of them are of legal age, and they are not considered highly vulnerable in the psychological aspect. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. *Privacy and Confidentiality.* This study observed the data Privacy Act of 2012 wherein the researcher assured that the data cannot be traced back to the participants which were the real source of information, to protect the identities of the participants. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the consent of the respondents. Thus, to ensure that no personal data would be exposed, the access was limited to the researcher alone. To protect the privacy of the participants, it was assured that the researcher is the only person that could access the survey results. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently deleted all the survey results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were

the real source of information. Risk, Benefits and Safety - In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and explained thoroughly and properly the purpose and benefits of the study as well as the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the survey questionnaire. The respondents, without restrictions, were able to ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire that was used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the respondents of the study. Likewise, this study is designed purely to collect academic information related to the study, and they were not asked for personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher made sure that the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire. The respondents were given the freedom not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological or emotional distress, and they would be free to withdraw as respondents to the study if they felt that they could not discuss the information that was being asked of them. The researcher valued their participation and placed their welfare as the highest priority during the course of the study. Justice. To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equally regardless of whether they would be respondents in the survey. The researcher was not prejudiced in choosing the respondents for the study. Anybody who fits the qualifications of being permanent-regular in the purposively selected schools. During the conduct of the study, the researcher made certain to respect the respondents by interrupting as little time as possible to the routine of the respondents. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, the researcher gave tokens of appreciation to the respondents. This token was an assortment of souvenir. The tokens were sent

via courier, and these were sealed carefully in a package. Also, each tokens were sanitized before being sent to your doorstep. Transparency. To provide transparency in this study, any type of communication in relation to the research was done with honesty and transparency. To safeguard the welfare of the participants, the researcher properly implemented the methods that are discussed in this study. All the necessary documents that supported the data analysis were included. Importantly, the researcher described the extent of the involvement of the respondents in this study and shared how the researcher-maintained objectivity in analyzing data and presenting the results of the study. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that the responses of the respondents were not influenced by any other factor like the conflict of interest. The findings of the study could be accessed by the respondents and school administrators of the participating schools because the information would be made available as long as they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the success of the study, the Division of Davao City was given a furnished copy of the results of the research so it can be accessed by the respondents and be used for learning and further study. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and learning materials which were ample and available in the conduct of the study and was done within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by encoding properly the ratings of the respondents during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results gathered were proficient and aligned that serves as a primary basis for adequacy. Community Involvement. It was a good practice to have community involvement during every phase of research, from planning to re-

porting. Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community, and community involvement will be accorded with primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate method to apply in their context, and use of the results or findings. The findings of this study would then be shared back with the community through gatherings, fora, and conferences.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in determining the extent of intercultural sensitivity, individual work performance, and teaching behavior of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City. Mean and standard deviation are descriptive statistics that tend to mea-

sure how the score clustered and scattered, respectively. This was use to supply the answer for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was utilized to determine the significance on the relationship among the three variables- intercultural sensitivity, individual work performance, and teaching behavior of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it is usually denoted by r . Hierarchical Regression Analysis. It was applied to evaluate the moderating effect of teaching behavior on the interaction of intercultural sensitivity and individual work performance of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study's objectives, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of intercultural sensitivity, individual work performance, and teaching behavior, the significant relationship among the variables, and the moderating effect of teaching behavior on the interaction between intercultural sensitivity and individual work performance of the teachers.

3.1. *Intercultural Sensitivity of Teachers Enjoyment*—This dimension has a category mean of 3.29, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as this particular domain of intercultural sensitivity of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City, is sometimes observed. In addition, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.71 to 3.76. The item, Interaction between people from different cultures, is a mutually rewarding experience. Reflects a mean rating of 2.71, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed among respondents in Calinan District, Davao City. The items, Taking part in

cross-cultural/multicultural activities, acquired a mean rating of 3.76, described as extensive and interpreted as an item is oftentimes observed. The result emphasizes that the teachers in Calinan District in Davao City sometimes can interact with individuals from different cultures. This result is consistent with the findings of Lindsey et al. (2010) that one of the characteristics of intercultural sensitive individuals is that they possess the ability to recognize the differences among students and families from different cultural groups, respond to those differences positively, and be able to interact effectively in a range of cultural environments.

3.2. *Confidence* —In particular, this dimension has a category mean of 3.40, interpreted as extensive, which means that in terms

of confidence, the intercultural sensitivity of the teachers in the Calinan District in Davao City is oftentimes observed. The mean ratings of the

Table 1. Intercultural Sensitivity in Terms of Enjoyment

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Interaction between people from different cultures is a mutually rewarding experience.	2.71	Moderately Extensive
Being interested in hearing about other cultures.	3.01	Moderately Extensive
Enjoying opportunities to interact with individuals from different cultures.	3.56	Extensive
Trying to obtain as much information as possible when interacting with people from different cultures.	3.21	Moderately Extensive
It is refreshing to learn new perspectives when interacting with someone from a different culture.	3.49	Extensive
Looking forward to interacting with people from different cultures.	3.41	Extensive
Enjoy interacting with people from different cultures.	3.14	Moderately Extensive
Taking part in cross-cultural/multicultural activities.	3.76	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.29	Moderately Extensive

items range from 2.67 to 3.92. The item, Finding it easy to talk in front of people from different cultures, reflects a mean rating of 2.67, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed among respondents in Calinan District in Davao City. Meanwhile, the item Feeling being encouraged when interacting with people from different cultures has a mean rating of 3.92, described as extensive and interpreted as often observed. The extensive

rating on intercultural sensitivity in terms of confidence implies that the teachers in Calinan District in Davao City oftentimes exhibit pleasant behavior when dealing with individuals with different cultural backgrounds. This finding is congruent with the view of Gillespie (2019). The intercultural sensitivity of a person affects their ability to recognize that others believe in different realities and truths separate from their own.

3.3. *Tolerance*—With respect to tolerance, it reflects a category mean of 3.39, which is described as moderately extensive, which is interpreted as this domain on intercultural sensitivity of teachers in Calinan District in Davao City is sometimes observed. It can be seen that the mean ratings of the different items range from

3.01 to 4.02. The item, Respecting the values of the people from different cultures, has a mean rating of 3.01, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. Whereas the item Thinking people from other cultures are also open-minded has a mean of 4.02, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed.

Table 2. Intercultural Sensitivity in Terms of Confidence

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Finding it easy to talk in front of people from different cultures.	2.67	Moderately Extensive
Engaging in situations where I will have to deal with culturally distinct people.	3.89	Extensive
I am pretty sure of myself when interacting with people from different cultures.	2.98	Moderately Extensive
Feeling rewarded when interacting with people from different cultures.	3.56	Extensive
Being as sociable as I want to be when interacting with people from different cultures.	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Feeling happy when interacting with someone from a different culture.	3.67	Extensive
Feeling confident when interacting with people from different cultures.	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Feeling encouraged when interacting with people from different cultures.	3.92	Extensive
Feeling a whole me when interacting with people from different cultures.	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.40	Extensive

The moderately extensive in this particular domain means that the ability to work towards understanding one’s values, strengths, and challenges regarding cultural differences that come from self-realization is oftentimes observed in Calinan District, Davao City. This finding supports the view of Reiche (2012) that self-knowledge is a means to becoming interculturally sensitive. Accordingly, understanding and becoming aware of one’s own cultural values, beliefs, attitudes, and judgment becomes central when we have to interact with people from different cultural backgrounds.

3.4. *Intercultural Sensitivity of Teachers*— Lastly, Table 4 summarizes the extent of teach-

ers’ intercultural sensitivity in Calinan District, Davao City. As shown in the table, the intercultural sensitivity of teachers obtained an overall mean score of 3.36, which was described as moderately extensive. Additionally, intercultural sensitivity of teachers in terms of confidence acquired the highest mean score of 3.40, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed, while intercultural sensitivity of teachers in terms of enjoyment, acquired the lowest mean score of 3.29, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed among teachers in Calinan District, Davao City.

The moderately extensive rating on intercultural sensitivity denotes that the ability to discriminate and experience relevant cultural

differences is sometimes observable among the teachers in the Calinan District in Davao City. The findings indicate that with moderately ex-

Table 3. Intercultural Sensitivity in Terms of Tolerance

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Respecting the values of people from different cultures.	3.01	Moderately Extensive
Being open-minded to people from different cultures.	3.08	Moderately Extensive
Liking to be with people from different cultures.	3.56	Extensive
Thinking people from other cultures are also open-minded.	4.02	Extensive
Accepting opinions of people from different cultures.	3.49	Extensive
Thinking my culture is as good as the culture of other people.	3.41	Extensive
Respecting the ways people from other cultures behave.	3.14	Moderately Extensive
Do not easily get upset when dealing with people from different cultures.	3.41	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.39	Moderately Extensive

Table 4. Summary Table on Intercultural Sensitivity of Teachers in Calinan District, Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Enjoyment	3.29	Moderately Extensive
Confidence	3.40	Extensive
Tolerance	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.36	Moderately Extensive

tensive intercultural sensitivity, teachers could successfully teach students from cultures other than their own. Adding more, the result agrees with Leavitt (2010) that intercultural sensitivity reacts to all levels, the importance of culture, the evaluation of cross-cultural relations, and the awareness of the motions arising from cultural differences, the inflation of cultural knowledge, and the modification to offer services to culturally unique needs.

3.5. *Individual Work Performance of the Teachers in Calinan District, Davao City—Task Performance*—Consequently, the dimension of task performance, as shown in Table 5, is de-

scribed as moderately extensive with a category mean of 3.55. This means that the teachers in Calinan District, Davao City sometimes manifest individual work performance in terms of task performance. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.64 to 3.84. Keeping in mind the results that I had noticed achieved in my work, the item reflects a mean rating of 2.64, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as this item oftentimes manifested by the teachers in Calinan District, Davao City. Further, the item Being able to perform my work well with minimal time and effort has a mean rating of 3.84, described as extensive and in-

terpreted as this item oftentimes manifested in Calinan District, Davao City. The result shows that the teachers in Calinan District, Davao City, could do their tasks sometimes because they managed to plan their work. These findings are congruent with Kuok and Taormina’s (2017) idea that one of the characteristics of extensive individual work performance is that time seems

to pass quickly at work for people who are work-engaged. Also, Clarke (2017) contends that being conscious of work performance promotes a higher level of self-exploration, guidance seeking, and other associated proactive career behaviors, which in turn may improve work readiness among newly hired employees.

Table 5. Individual Work Performance of Teachers in Terms of Task Performance

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Managing to plan my work so that it was done on time.	3.22	Moderately Extensive
My planning was optional.	3.56	Extensive
Keeping in mind the results that I had noticed achieved in my work.	2.64	Moderately Extensive
Keeping in mind the results that I had noticed achieved in my work.	3.13	Moderately Extensive
Knowing how to set the right priorities.	3.62	Extensive
Being able to perform my work well with minimal time and effort.	3.84	Extensive
Collaboration with others was very productive.	3.46	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.35	Moderately Extensive

3.6. *Contextual Performance*—This particular domain of individual work performance of teachers, as shown in Table 7, reflects an extensive category mean of 3.48, which means that it is oftentimes manifested. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.72 to 4.04. The table further reveals that the item Taking on challenging work tasks, when available, has a mean rating of 2.72, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as an item sometimes manifested by the respondents in Calinan District, Davao City. Meanwhile, the item, Grasping opportunities when they presented themselves, reflects a mean rating of 4.04, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested in Calinan District, Davao City. The result means that teachers in Calinan District in Davao City oftentimes

show support on the organizational, social and psychological environment of the school. This finding is congruent with the view of Boyd et al. (2011) that such working conditions, including behavioral climate and administrative support, were found to have a negative impact on teacher turnover rates, especially among novice educators working in schools with low-income and low-achieving students. Also, the result agrees with Rossi’s (2018) assertion that inter-organizational connections, such as relationships between co-teachers, school heads, stakeholders, and even students, which teachers build with one another during their work time, were found to influence their willingness to remain in the profession strongly. The stronger these links are, the more difficult it is to give up these links, and thus, it is more difficult to leave.

Table 6. Individual Work Performance of Teachers in Terms of Contextual Performance

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Taking extra responsibilities.	3.56	Extensive
I started new tasks myself when my old ones were finished.	3.55	Extensive
Taking on challenging work tasks when available.	2.72	Moderately Extensive
Working at keeping my job knowledge up-to-date.	3.41	Extensive
Working at keeping my job skills up-to-date.	3.12	Moderately Extensive
Coming up with creative solutions to new problems.	3.92	Extensive
I keep looking for new challenges in my job.	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Doing more than was expected of me.	3.65	Extensive
Being actively participative in work meetings.	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Looking actively for ways to improve my performance at work	3.56	Extensive
Grasping opportunities when they presented themselves.	4.04	Extensive
Knowing how to solve difficult situations and setbacks quickly.	3.67	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.48	Extensive

3.7. *Productive Work Behavior*—This domain, as shown in Table 7, has a category mean of 3.82, described as extensive and interpreted that this particular domain of individual work performance of teachers is oftentimes manifested in Calinan District, Davao City. Adding on, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.03 to 3.85. Specifically, the item, Doing

more than was expected of me a mean rating of 3.03 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as item sometimes manifested by the teachers in Calinan District, Davao City. The item, Speaking with colleagues about the positive aspects of my work, reflects a mean rating of 3.85, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested by the respondents in Calinan District, Davao City.

The result indicates that the teachers in Calinan District in Davao City oftentimes exhibit behavior that does not harm the well-being of the organization. This finding agrees with the proposition of Biggs, Brough, and Barbour (2014) that individual maintains a high level of work engagement if they exhibit positive behavior because they are engaged in their work and

put high levels of energy and enthusiasm into what they do, the feeling of self-worth increasing their intention to stay. Thus, these working individuals translated sufficient job resources into high work engagement and further lead to positive job outcomes both in personal and organizational performance.

Table 7. Individual Work Performance of Teachers in Terms of Productive Work Behavior

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
I never complained about unimportant matters at work.	3.44	Extensive
I don't make problems greater than they were at work.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
Focusing on the positive aspects of a work situation instead of on the negative aspects.	3.51	Extensive
Speaking with colleagues about the positive aspects of my work.	3.85	Extensive
Speaking with people from outside the organization about the positive aspects of my work.	3.62	Extensive
Doing more than was expected of me.	3.03	Moderately Extensive
Managed to finish the tasks ahead of time.	3.59	Extensive
Making use of my time to do work during office hours.	3.41	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.46	Extensive

3.8. *Individual Work Performance of Teachers*—Lastly as shown in the Table 8 is the summary on the extent of individual work performance of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City. As shown in the table, individual work performance of the teachers obtained an overall mean score of 3.87 with a descriptive rating of extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested by the teachers in Calinan District, Davao City. Adding more, results on Table 8 show that individual work performance in terms of contextual performance acquired the highest mean score of 3.48 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested, while, individual work performance in terms of task

performance acquired the lowest mean score of 3.35 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by teachers in Calinan District, Davao City. The result indicates that the behaviors or actions of a teacher that are relevant to the goals of the organization are oftentimes manifested. This finding agrees with Christian et al. (2011) that the teachers' work performance can be a motivational concept that could lead to the voluntary allocation of personal resources directed at the range of tasks demanded in the teaching profession. Also, this supports the view of Esen (2011) that teachers who have high regard for their performance in teaching jobs are more dedicated to the school organization.

Table 9 shows the extent of teaching behavior of teachers reflects an overall mean of 3.56, described as extensive. The mean ratings of the items range from 3.43 to 3.70. The item, Feel-

ing a moral obligation to give a full day's work for a full day's pay reflects a mean rating of 3.43 described as extensive, interpreted as item is oftentimes evident. Meanwhile, the item, Be-

Table 8. Summary Table on Individual Work Performance of Teachers in Calinan District, Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Task Performance	3.35	Moderately Extensive
Contextual Performance	3.48	Extensive
Productive Work Behavior	3.46	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.43	Extensive

believing that work provides a powerful channel to express one’s knowledge, ability, and creativity, shows a mean rating of 3.70, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes evident. The result suggests that the behavioral rules that create a positive environment at work among teachers is oftentimes evident. The finding is in consonance to the view of Petty and Hill (2017) that a strong positive behavior can lead to employees being fairly treated, which in turn motivates them and develops a sense of loyalty towards the organization. Consequently, an individual with strong positive work ethic is an employee who has a high commitment to an organization and subsequently more likely to make changes where such changes do not have the potential to change the basic values and goals of the organization and is considered beneficial for the organization, compared to individuals who are less supportive work ethic and less committed to their organization that is more likely to make changes.

Table 9. Summary on Teaching Behavior of Teachers in Calinan District, Davao City

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Believing that one’s work provides the best source of achieving perfection in life.	3.63	Extensive
Considering teaching career to be one of the most important activities in my life.	3.45	Extensive
Believing that a job well done is a reward in itself.	3.60	Extensive
Believing that work provides a powerful channel to express one’s knowledge, ability and creativity.	3.70	Extensive
Feeling a moral obligation to give a full day’s work for a full day’s pay.	3.43	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.56	Extensive

3.10. *Relationship among Intercultural Sensitivity, Individual Work Performance, and Teaching Behavior of Teachers in Calinan District, Davao City* —The results of the analysis of the relationship among intercultural sensitivity, individual work performance, and teaching behavior of teachers in Calinan District,

Davao City, are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson product-moment correlation was utilized to determine the relationship among the variables mentioned. Meanwhile, Table 10 shows that intercultural sensitivity has a significant positive relationship with the individual work performance of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City with a p-value of .000 that

is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .954, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of the intercultural sensitivity, individual work performance of the teachers also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of null hypothesis of no significant relationship between intercultural sensitivity and individual work performance of teachers in Calinan Dis-

trict, Davao City. This finding agreed with the view of Liu (2016) employees with high level of intercultural sensitivity became the catalysts for teamwork which are able to promote team communication and improve work enthusiasm. They can more easily become the tacit cooperation object and a close friend with other team members.

Table 10. Relationship among Intercultural Sensitivity, Individual Work Performance, and Teaching Behavior of Teachers in Calinan District, Davao City

Variables	Individual Work Performance	Teaching Behavior
Intercultural Sensitivity	0.954** (0.000)	0.970** (0.000)
Individual Work Performance	1	0.975** (0.000)

**Significant at $p < 0.05$

On the one hand, the result shows that the relationship between intercultural sensitivity and the teaching behavior of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City, has a significant positive relationship with a p-value of .00 that is less than the alpha set at .05 ($r = 0.970, p < 0.05$). This means that if the extent of the teaching quality of teachers changes, the extent of the teaching behavior of teachers also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the teaching quality of teachers and the teaching behavior of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City. The findings are in consonance with the study of Spilt et al. (2011) that teachers have a basic need for relatedness with the students in their class and hence suggest that individual teacher-student relationships may affect the professional and personal self-esteem of teachers. On the other hand, the result shows that the relationship between teaching behavior has a significant positive relationship with the individual work performance of teachers in Calinan

District, Davao City, with a p-value of .00 that is less than alpha set at .05 ($r = 0.975, p < .05$). This means that if the extent of teaching behavior changes, individual work performance of the teachers also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teaching behavior has a significant positive relationship with the individual work performance of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City. This finding supports the view of Gemora (2014), who suggests that people who are interpersonally competent are more likely to build and use networks of relationships that provide support in the face of stressful life events.

3.11. Moderating Effect of Teaching Behavior on the Interaction Between Intercultural Sensitivity and Individual Work Performance of Teachers in Calinan District, Davao City — The moderating effect of teaching behavior (TB) on the relationship between intercultural sensitivity (IS) and individual work performance (IWP) of teachers in Calinan District, Davao

City, was tested using hierarchical regression analysis. Results in Table 12 show that the Beta coefficients for the Step 1 analysis of intercultural sensitivity (IS) and individual work performance (IWP) were = 0.131, S.E. = 0.052, $p < 0.05$; and teaching behavior (TB) and individual work performance (IWP) of teachers were = 0.807, S.E.=0.049, $p < 0.05$. When intercultural sensitivity (IS) and teaching behavior (TB) were included as the only independent variables (without including an interaction term), the regression model explained 95.20 percent of the variance in individual work performance (IWP) of teachers ($R^2 = 0.952$, $p < .05$).

Table 11. Moderating Effect of Teaching Behavior on the Interaction Between Intercultural Sensitivity and Individual Work Performance of Teachers in Calinan District, Davao City

Step	Variable	B	Beta	S.E.	p-value
Step 1	Individual Work Performance (IWP)				
	Intercultural Sensitivity (IS)	.131**	.130	.052	.013 (Reject H0)
	Teaching Behavior (TB)	.807**	.849	.049	.000 (Reject H0)
	R² = 0.952	F-value = 2972.001**	p-value = 0.000		
Step 2	Intercultural Sensitivity (IS)	.136**	.036	.102	.021 (Reject H0)
	Teaching Behavior (TB)	.636**	.669	.102	.000 (Reject H0)
	Moderator (IS*TB)	.140**	.345	.021	.007 (Reject H0)
	R² = 0.953	F-value = 2000.007**	p-value = 0.000		

**Significant at $p < 0.05$

Moreover, Beta coefficients for the Step 2 analysis of intercultural sensitivity (IS) and individual work performance (IWP) of teachers were = 0.136, S.E. = .102, $p < 0.05$; teaching behavior (TB) and individual work performance (IWP) of teachers were = 0.636, S.E. = 0.102, $p < 0.05$; and moderator (IS*TB) and individual work performance (IWP) of teachers were = 0.140, S.E.= 0.021, $p < 0.05$. Also, it was indicated that when an interaction between inter-

cultural sensitivity (IS) and teaching behavior (TB) was added, the percentage of variance in individual work performance (IWP) was 95.30 percent ($R^2 = 0.953$; $p < 0.05$) indicated the independent contribution of each variable while controlling for the influence of others to create the regression equation for each analysis, after assuring significance by examining accompanying p-values. Hence, the interaction term accounted for an additional 0.10 percent of the variance in the dependent variable ($R^2 = 0.001$). Based on the result, the null hypothesis was rejected as teaching behavior (TB) had significantly moderated the relationship between intercultural sensitivity (IS) and individual work performance (IWP) of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City. The significant role of teaching behavior as a moderator in the relationship between intercultural sensitivity and individual work performance of teachers is contributed to by the fact that there exists a relationship among these variables. It is emphasized in this study that teaching behavior is an undeniable factor that strengthens the relationship between intercultural sensitivity and individual work performance. According to Yu and Chen (2010), an individual's sensitivity to cultural differences is reflected as an important factor that influences

one's preference for a particular style of handling conflict. The more sensitive people perceive themselves to be, the more likely they are to use integrating and compromising strategies to manage conflict and the less likely they are to use avoiding and dominating styles. Meanwhile, Sammons (2011) argued that intercultural sensitivity has a positive impact on the social connectedness of working individuals. In this sense, intercultural sensitivity of certain individuals may mediate the effects of stress by making different coping mechanisms available to their members. Some ways that cultures differ in this respect are beliefs that allow them to make sense of stressors, beliefs about how stressors should be coped with, and the availability of social support. Lastly, the result of the study supports the notion of Krush et al. (2013) that resilience attenuates the debilitating effects of stress on an employee's work performance. Accordingly, resilient people can effectively regulate their emotions when faced with adversity, or even though resilient people experience negative emotions at levels comparable to those of their less resilient peers when faced with a stressor, they also experience more positive emotions.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The literature supported the discussions in the first chapters, and the conclusions were based on the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to assess the moderating effect of teaching behavior on the interaction between intercultural sensitivity and individual work performance of teachers utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using a correlation technique. The researcher selected the 169 elementary school teachers in Calinan District in the Division of Davao City as the respon-

dents through a random sampling method. The researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Overall, the results showed that the extent of intercultural sensitivity of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City, has an overall mean of 3.36 and a descriptive rating of moderately extensive.

Also, intercultural sensitivity in terms of enjoyment, confidence, and tolerance obtained mean scores of 3.29, 3.40, and 3.39, respectively. The extent of individual work performance of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City, has an overall mean of 3.43 with an extensive descriptive rating. Also, individual work performance in terms of task performance, contextual performance, and productive work behavior obtained mean scores of 3.35, 3.48, and 3.46, respectively. Descriptive analysis indicated that the extent of the moderating variable, which is the teaching behavior of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City, has an overall mean of 3.56 with an extensive descriptive rating. On the one hand, the result showed intercultural sensitivity has a significant positive relationship with the individual work performance of teachers in Calinan District in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .954$, $p < 0.05$). On the one hand, intercultural sensitivity has a significant positive relationship with the teaching behavior of teachers in Calinan District in Davao City with a p-value of .000, which is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .970$, $p < 0.05$). On the other hand, teaching behavior has a significant positive relationship with the individual work performance of teachers in Calinan District in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .975$, $p < 0.05$). On the other hand, findings reflected that teaching behavior is a significant moderator on the interaction between intercultural sensitivity and individual work performance of teachers in Calinan District in Davao City. The analysis showed that when an interaction between intercultural sensitivity (IS) and teaching behavior (TB) was added, the percentage of variance in individual work performance (IWP) was 95.30 percent ($R^2 = 0.952$; $p < 0.05$), indicating the independent contribution of each variable while controlling for the influence of others to create the

regression equation for each analysis, after assuring significance by examining accompanying p-values. Hence, the interaction term accounted for an additional 0.10 percent of the variance in the dependent variable ($R^2 = 0.001$).

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study and within the limitations and restrictions (such as the survey questionnaire and number of participants), several conclusions are generated: The intercultural sensitivity of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City, was moderately extensive. Intercultural sensitivity of teachers in terms of enjoyment and confidence belongs to an extensive rating. In contrast, intercultural sensitivity of teachers in terms of enjoyment and tolerance was rated moderately extensive. The moderately extensive rating on intercultural sensitivity denotes that the ability to discriminate and experience relevant cultural differences is sometimes observable among the teachers in Calinan District in Davao City. The individual work performance of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City, was rated as extensive. Individual work performance of teachers in terms of contextual performance and productive work behavior acquired extensive ratings. In contrast, individual work performance in terms of task performance belongs to moderately extensive ratings. The result indicates that the behaviors or actions of a teacher that are relevant to the goals of the organization are oftentimes manifested. Furthermore, the extent of teachers' teaching behavior in Calinan District, Davao City, acquired extensive rating. The result suggests that the behavioral rules that create a positive environment at work among teachers are often evident. Meanwhile, intercultural sensitivity has a positive significant relationship with teachers' individual work performance and teaching behavior in Calinan District, Davao City. Also, teaching behavior has a positive significant relationship with the individual work performance of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City. Lastly, teaching behavior has

a significant moderating effect on the relationship between intercultural sensitivity and the individual work performance of teachers. It is emphasized in this study that teaching behavior is an undeniable factor that intervened in the interaction between intercultural sensitivity and individual work performance of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City.

4.3. Recommendations—The researcher may recommend that policymakers allocate resources for ongoing professional development programs focusing on modern teaching methods, technology integration, and pedagogical innovation. They should also provide incentives for teachers to participate in continuous learning and implement fair and comprehensive teacher evaluation systems that include classroom observations and student performance data. Finally, they should ensure that feedback is constructive and supports professional growth. School heads may develop a clear educational vision for the school and communicate it to the staff, students, and parents. They may also provide strong leadership that aligns with the school's mission. In addition, they may provide opportunities for teachers to engage in professional development,

both within and outside the school. They may encourage them to attend workshops, conferences, and seminars. Further, support staff and support staff training would be essential, and they should be a part of the strategy being developed for educational systems development. This type of support would best allow teachers to integrate technology in meaningful ways at the classroom level. Furthermore, the researcher may suggest that school heads should conduct performance reviews regularly. Individual work performance is essential to measuring teachers' performance; thus, schools may hold individual meetings to let them know where they excel and what areas they need to work on. Lastly, researchers may conduct further analysis on the factors that may contribute to the interaction between intercultural sensitivity and individual work performance of teachers in Calinan District, Davao City, since it was found that when the interaction between intercultural sensitivity (IS) and teaching behavior (TB) was added, the percentage of variance in individual work performance (IWP) of teachers was only 95.30 percent.

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